

Effect of spray volume (0.75 kg a.i./ha) on mortality of brown planthoppers. IRRI insectary, 1980.

Insecticide and volume (liters/ha)	Mortality ^a (%)				
	1 DAT	5 DAT	10 DAT	15 DAT	20 DAT
Carbofuran 12 F					
1000	100 a	98 a	90 a	62 a	20 a
500	100 a	99 a	92 a	68 a	27 a
250	94 a	36 b	14 b	9 b	0 b
Perthane 45 EC					
1000	100 a	98 a	41 a	16 ab	2 a
500	98 a	84 a	39 a	30 a	8 a
250	100 a	93 a	39 a	7 b	0 a
Monocrotophos 30 EC					
1000	94 ab	32 a	10 a	7 a	2 a
500	95 a	28 a	7 a	3 a	2 a
250	83 b	26 a	0 a	2 a	0 a
UC54229 100 Tech.					
1000	99 a	100 a	91 a	55 a	25 a
500	100 a	99 a	82 a	42 ab	9 a
250	98 a	82 b	58 b	23 b	5 a

^aAdjusted using Abbott's formula. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. DAT = days after treatment.

Mortality for three volumes of Perthane and monocrotophos spray was similar (see table). However, carbofuran and UC54229 usually were most toxic when applied at 1,000 and 500 liters. ■

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Soil and crop management

Effects of phosphorus fertilizer sources in calcareous soil

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A field experiment on calcareous silty clay soil (pH 7.7, OM 0.4% Ca 23.0 meq/100 g, Mg 13.0 meq/ 100 g, CEC 15 meq/100 g, and Olsen P 4.2 ppm) evaluated two sources of phosphate fertilizer: diammonium phosphate (DAP) and triple superphosphate (TSP). Urea was applied as a nitrogen source with TSP.

Fertilizer treatments were randomized in a complete block design with four

Effect of sources of phosphate fertilizer on plant height, tiller number, plant phosphorus concentration 30 days after transplanting, and grain yield of rice in calcareous soil in Malaysia.^a

Source of P fertilizer ^b	Plant ht (cm)	Tillers (no./hill)	P concentration (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
None (control)	25 c	18 c	0.15 c	3.0 c
DAP	38 b	34 b	0.17 b	4.5 b
TSP	45 a	39 a	0.18 a	5.1 a
CV %	3.61	3.02	1.41	2.97

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bControl = 120 kg N/ha and no P, DAP = diammonium phosphate, TSP = triple superphosphate + urea.

replications. Nitrogen and phosphorus levels were 120 kg N/ha and 60 kg P₂O₅/ha. All of the P and half the N were broadcast and incorporated into the soil two days before IR6 seedlings were transplanted. The remaining N was topdressed at the time of panicle

initiation.

The number of tillers per hill, plant height, percent plant P concentration at 30 days after transplanting (DT), and grain yield increased significantly with the combination of urea and TSP (see table). ■

Rice germination and seedling response to oxygen in floodwater

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Germination and establishment of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) seedlings are usually less than optimum in water-saturated and flooded soils, apparently because of

a deficiency of available oxygen (O₂). This study evaluated the effect of specific O₂ levels on seedling development and identified rice cultivars that may be more tolerant of the low O₂ concentrations associated with water-saturated rice soils.

Gas flowmeters and regulators allow mixing of air and N₂ gas. Six O₂ levels — 21, 10.5, 5.3, 2.0, 1.0, and 0% (99.995% N₂ gas) — were bubbled into a transparent plastic box (36 × 28 × 9 cm deep) holding deionized water 7.5 cm

deep. Seeds of 4 rice cultivars were suspended on cheesecloth about 3 cm below the water surface. As gas of desired O₂ concentration dispersed into the box, the water circulated slowly. Water circulation plus a thin transparent polyethylene cover helped assure that O₂ concentration within each box was uniform. A YSI Model 53 O₂ meter monitored O₂ levels continuously. Seed boxes were placed in a growth chamber providing light intensity of 400 microeinsteins/m² per second, a 12-hour day,